

RDA Data Stewardship Organisational Models Survey Final

Start of Block: Default Question Block

RDA Data Stewardship Organisational Models Survey

Welcome to the survey!

You are being invited to take part in a study examining the provision of data stewardship services internationally. Data stewardship comes in many forms and contexts, but all have a common goal of supporting good data management. Yet, the diversity of such roles and contexts can make it hard for the research data management community to professionalise our work and services further.

This research is being led by the Research Data Alliance's 'Professionalising Data Stewardship' Interest Group (the Survey Team). The survey has been created by Bill Ayres, Iryna Kuchma, Liise Lehtsalu, Graham Parton, Adam Száldobágyi, Angus Whyte and Niklas Zimmer.

Before you decide to take part, it is important that you understand why the research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

What is the purpose of this research?

The aim of this study is to gain insight into how services deploy staff roles and resources to achieve the goal(s) of data stewardship in a way that meets the needs of stakeholders and the targeted research communities' requirements.

Why have I been invited to take part and what does my participation involve?

You have been invited to take part because you are subscribed to a public mailing list relevant to data stewardship, e.g. the RDA Interest Group on Professionalising Data Stewardship. You are asked to complete an online questionnaire. It will take an average of 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire.

Do I need to take part?

No – it is entirely up to you. Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. If you wish to withdraw from this study whilst completing the survey, you can do so at any time by exiting the online questionnaire (close the window). Due to the method of data collection, following submission of the questionnaire it will not be possible to withdraw your data from the study which are already collected because we will not be able to identify your responses. Deciding not

to take part or withdrawing from the study whilst completing it will not affect you in any way.

Are there any risks or disadvantages associated with taking part?

Given that the data gathered includes specific questions about institutional services for data stewardship there is a small risk of identifiability. To mitigate this risk no statistical reporting of small numbers will take place and access to the data is limited to the survey team members only (please see below how the data are managed). Furthermore, all questions are voluntary and you can choose which questions to answer. We will only use the sections that you do complete.

What are the potential benefits of taking part in the research?

There are no direct benefits, but the findings will be shared with the RDA community to inform models and strategies to best support the professionalisation of data stewardship.

Will my taking part be kept confidential?

Your data will be processed in accordance with The Data Protection Act 2018, which is the UK's implementation of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and the data is collected under public task. All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. The research data (questionnaire responses) will be downloaded from the Qualtrics XM survey tool, anonymised and stored on the University of Manchester's Secure Data Service storage system.

The study is funded through in-kind contribution of effort from the members of the RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group, including support from the project FAIRsFAIR "Fostering FAIR Data Practices In Europe", which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020 Grant agreement 831558.

The University of Manchester will be using information from you in order to undertake this study and will act as the data controller for this study. This means we are responsible for looking after your information and using it properly. The University conducts research to the highest standards of research integrity within a research culture that values knowledge-creation for its own sake; for the potential benefits it promises humankind; and for the ways it enriches higher learning. We promise to respect the confidentiality and sensitivity of the personal information that you, as a participant in our research, provide to us; that we get from other organisations; and that we share with other collaborating organisations, such as other universities or our research funders. For general information about how we use your data go to the [Privacy Notice](#).

What are your choices about how your information is used?

You can stop being part of the study at any time whilst completing the survey, without giving a reason, but we will keep information about you that we already have.

What will happen to the information collected and the results of the study?

The data collected will provide insight into the delivery of support for data stewardship among

the organisations participating in the survey. The survey findings will identify variations in models of support, according to national and other contextual factors. Please note that you and your organisation will NOT be identifiable in any of these findings. The results of the study may also be published in scientific journals and/or presented at research conferences. You will not be identifiable from any published results. With your consent, the anonymous data may also be pooled with data collected in the future, and used in subsequent ethically approved projects. A summary of the findings from the study will be made available to participants via the RDA website.

Who has approved this study?

This survey falls under the category of market research for which formal ethical review and approval is not required by the University of Manchester. More information on this can be found [here](#).

Who can I contact?

If you have any further questions about the study prior to participating, then please contact [Dr Graham Parton](#) on behalf of the survey team.

If you would like to discuss this study with someone independent of the study, or make a complaint about the study then please contact:

research.ethics@manchester.ac.uk

The results of this survey will be anonymised and made publicly available under the licence: Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International ([CC BY-SA 4.0](#))

In order to complete the survey, please indicate that you provide informed consent for participation by indicating 'Yes'. Selecting 'No' will take you to the end of the survey without any information being recorded, or you can simply close this window.

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided above about this study
- I have been given the opportunity to consider the information provided, ask questions, and have had these questions answered to my satisfaction.
- I understand that my participation is entirely voluntary, and that I can withdraw at any time just by exiting the questionnaire, without giving a reason and without my employment or legal rights being affected.
- I understand that my submitted raw data will be stored securely until the end of 2022 or the end of the Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group, whichever is the earliest.

- I understand that my anonymised data may also be pooled with data collected in the future, and used in subsequent ethically approved projects.
- I understand that if I complete and submit the questionnaire, I cannot have my responses removed at a later date.
- I agree to take part in the above study

Yes, I consent to participation in this survey (1)

No, I do not consent to participation in this survey (2)

Do you agree to your responses being included in the anonymised dataset? This does not affect your ability to participate. Please select 'Yes' or 'No'.

Yes (1)

No (2)

The Survey Team may wish to follow up with survey respondents, including inviting responses to be included in related follow-on work. If you are happy for us follow-up, please provide a suitable central or named contact email address below, e.g. Helpdesk, shared team mailbox. (This does not affect your ability to participate)

End of Block: Default Question Block

Start of Block: Block 1

Section 1 - basic information about the 'service'/data stewardship provision

These questions aim to capture essential information about the nature of your service that relates to data stewardship.

Service Type

What is the name of your service?

Question 1

What organisational level is your service at? (select all that apply):

- Research group (1)
- Departmental (2)
- Inter-departmental (3)
- Institutional (4)
- Multi-institutional (5)
- National (6)
- Multi-national (7)
- Global (8)

Question 2

How specific is your service to given research domains?:

- Generic service / domain agnostic (1)
- Multi-domain (2)
- Single domain (3)
- Project / sub-domain specific (4)

Question 3

What service type keywords (scope) best describe your service/provision? (select all that apply):

- Repository service (1)
 - Advisory service (2)
 - Training service (3)
 - Centralised service (4)
 - De-centralised service (5)
 - Federated service (6)
 - Research infrastructure (7)
 - Publisher-related service (8)
 - Government service (9)
 - Other (generic, separated key phrases only please) (10)
-

Question 4

Which global regions are your main activities focused within? (select all that apply):

- Africa (1)
 - Asia (2)
 - Australasia (3)
 - Europe (4)
 - North America (5)
 - South America (6)
-

Question 5

Is your service based in a specific country (leave blank if not applicable)?

▼ Afghanistan (1) ... Zimbabwe (1357)

End of Block: Block 1

Start of Block: Block 2

Section 2 - data stewardship roles/functions within your context

This section addresses data stewardship roles; 'customers'/target groups of your service; value or benefits promoted; levels of engagement with data stewardship; maturity of service provision; and resourcing.

Consider the following diagram which shows how data stewardship roles may exist in the intersections of different research data areas:

(Image credit [Frederike Schmitz. \(2020\)](#) via Zenodo)

For each of the following broad roles of data stewardship please list any relevant job titles within your service (Note: the figure mentions job titles but we know that these vary greatly):

Question 6

Main service delivery roles to provide "traditional" RDM support and services, e.g. :

- advice, training and advocacy on good research data management practice
- managing a research data repository
- engagement with researchers to understand their RDM needs
- advising on completion of data management plans (DMPs)
- reporting and providing information on research data outputs.

What are the job titles of people in your organisation involved in this?

Question 7

Delivering policy change on RDM, FAIR and open science across the organisation, e.g. :

- aligning researchers' data handling with data policies
- working with policy stakeholders to define policies and compliance requirements
- ensuring capacity among support staff to advise research stakeholders on adopting data workflows, tools, standards and infrastructure.

What are the job titles of people in your organisation involved in this?

Question 8

Providing support, training and consultancy to enable change in research workflows and practices, e.g. :

- aligning researchers' needs and required data infrastructure
- working with research stakeholders to support the adoption of data workflows, tools, standards and infrastructure
- working with infrastructure stakeholders to facilitate software and hardware services and technical infrastructure.

What are the job titles of people in your organisation involved in this?

Question 9

Liaising between policy stakeholders and data centres, repositories or other research data infrastructures to deliver compliant services, e.g. :

- aligning data policies and features of data services and infrastructure
- working with infrastructure stakeholders to assess needs for software and hardware services and technical infrastructure
- working with policy stakeholders to define policies and compliance requirements.

What are the job titles of people in your organisation involved in this?

Question 10

Does your service have any other relevant roles beyond those defined above? (for each one please also indicate associated job titles)

Question 11

Which of the following customer groups or service users do you provide data stewardship services for? (Choose all that apply)

	Never (1)	Infrequently (2)	Occasionally (3)	Frequently (4)	Very frequently (5)
Students (including Postgraduates) (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Funded producers of data (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Unfunded producers of data (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Science communicators; journalists (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Commercial users (5)	<input type="radio"/>				
Government/policy users (6)	<input type="radio"/>				
Affiliated researchers; members of your organisation (7)	<input type="radio"/>				
Wider community; lay investigators; citizen scientists; teachers of the faculties (8)	<input type="radio"/>				
General public (9)	<input type="radio"/>				

Question 12

Data stewardship support you provide

What data stewardship actions does your service provide to the community? (Choose all that apply)

- Defining the policy and research data governance environments (1)
 - Supporting data management planning e.g. DMP creation and review, data curation at project end point (2)
 - Supporting data management documentation and traceability (3)
 - Developing a sustainable business model for a trustworthy service (4)
 - Professionalising RDM training and engagement (5)
 - Defining interoperability frameworks - metadata, versioning, standards and identifiers (6)
 - Guidance about selecting data, services and tools for data management (7)
 - Ensuring good practice in versioning, curation and archiving (8)
 - Providing (linked) data catalogues for accessing the data (9)
-

Question 13

Rate your service's level of engagement with end-users for the following stages of the research project lifecycle, drawn from the Jisc "Research Data Management Toolkit" (0 = little or no engagement; 4 = actively engaged level)

	0 (1)	1 (2)	2 (3)	3 (4)	4 (5)
Plan and design (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Collect and capture (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Collaborate and analyse (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Manage, store and preserve (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Share and publish (5)	<input type="radio"/>				
Discover, reuse and cite (6)	<input type="radio"/>				

Question 14

What value or benefits of data stewardship does your organisation promote to its users/customers? (select all that apply)

- Sustainable long term digital preservation (1)
 - Contribution to data and metadata quality (2)
 - Risks effectively managed (3)
 - Resource use efficiency (4)
 - Research visibility / citation (5)
 - Knowledge transfer enhanced (6)
 - Compliance with funder policy (7)
 - Research integrity, transparency and reproducibility (8)
 - Enhanced value from data linking (9)
 - Legal and regulatory compliance e.g. privacy, access to information (10)
 - Support to meet FAIR principles (11)
 - Other (12) _____
-

Service initiation and engagement

Question 15

Which of the following do you see as key factors for successfully initiating data stewardship support in your organisation?

- Research centres have developed data stewardship practices relevant to their domain (1)
 - The community or organisation has policies relating to data management (2)
 - Research centres use research tools or services offered by the organisation (3)
 - Key skills and knowledge for data stewardship are available (4)
 - Training services or networks are available for building the key skills and knowledge (5)
 - Senior management see the value in data stewardship (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

Question 16

What level of engagement does your service have with developments in stewardship practices, policies and standards relevant to the communities it serves? (select one)

- Awareness: the service monitors data stewardship practice in the community or communities it serves and makes local practitioners aware of it. (1)
 - Adoption: the service or its host organisation also supports data stewardship practitioners to embed community practice locally. (2)
 - Collaboration: the service also engages with the design, development, and review of data stewardship practice in the communities served. Consults and collaborates widely, potentially also taking a community coordination and leadership role. (3)
-

Question 17

What are the main factors that influence your service's ability to engage with research data producers?

Service maturity

Question 18

How mature are the service's data stewardship capabilities, in terms of the level of alignment with broader standards and practices of the commissioning organisation? Please rate the maturity of each area of data stewardship capability according to this scale:

0 (no coverage or service)

1 (initial: new or immature service, but intention to develop and to address performance issues)

2 (managed: complete coverage of this area but service may be limited, performance objectives are actively identified and monitored)

3 (defined: comprehensive coverage via a fully developed service aligned with overall organisational standards and practice, and with performance objectives that reflect this)

	0 (1)	1 (2)	2 (3)	3 (4)
Defining the policy and research data governance environment (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supporting data management planning e.g. DMP creation and review, data curation at project end point (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supporting data management documentation and traceability (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Developing a sustainable business model for a trustworthy service (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Professionalising RDM training and engagement (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Defining interoperability frameworks - metadata, versioning, standards & identifiers (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Guidance about selecting data, services and tools for data management (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ensuring good practice in versioning, curation and archiving (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Providing
(linked) data
catalogues for
accessing the
data (9)

Resourcing the service: people and costs

Question 19

How many FTEs (full-time equivalent staff) does your service allocate to supporting data stewardship?

- < 1 (1)
- 1 - 2 (2)
- 3 - 5 (3)
- 6 - 10 (4)
- > 10 (5)
- Don't know (6)
- Not applicable (7)

Question 20

What is the scale of the data provider/producer user community that your service supports annually (in terms of numbers of DMPs, projects and researchers)?

Not Applicable

0 10002000300040005000600070008000900010000

Data Management Plans (DMPs) ()	
Projects ()	
Researchers ()	

Question 21

Roughly, how many unique users access your datasets annually (select n/a for advisory services)

- < 100 (1)
 - 100 - 1000 (2)
 - 1001 - 10,000 (3)
 - 10,000 + (4)
 - Don't know (5)
 - Not applicable (6)
-

Question 22

Considering how data stewardship support is resourced by your organisation, which of the following statements apply? This question refers to financial costs (select all that apply)

- Recurring dedicated budget is made available for data stewardship (1)
- Fixed-term budget for a commissioned service (2)
- Direct costs to research grants or projects (3)
- Allocated overheads from research grants or projects (4)
- Fixed-term development grant / seed funding (5)
- Volunteer effort (6)
- Don't know (7)
- Other (8) _____

End of Block: Block 2

Start of Block: Block 3

Section 3 - capturing the wider context

This section covers the stakeholders for your organisation's data stewardship; factors that could increase data stewardship adoption; barriers to developing the support; and your experience of key factors for successful data management adoption/engagement.

Question 23

Which of the following key stakeholders are involved with the governance of your data stewardship service? (select all that apply)

- Host organisation (1)
 - Funders (2)
 - Advisory or steering group (3)
 - User group (4)
 - Research ethics committee (5)
 - Data access committee (6)
 - Legal / data protection office (7)
 - Other (please specify) (8) _____
-

Question 24

Which of the following key communities are you involved with in providing your data stewardship service? (select all that apply)

Research infrastructures (1)

Professional networks (2)

Research funders (3)

Publishers (4)

Societies and associations (5)

National and / or international e-infrastructures (6)

Libraries (7)

Other (please specify) (8) _____

Increasing adoption

Question 25

Which of the following would you expect to help increase the adoption of data stewardship practices by your users? (select all that apply)

- Exemplars from communities with well-developed data stewardship practices (1)
 - The community has developed policies for data management (2)
 - Uptake of tools/services that help produce outputs based on good data stewardship practice (3)
 - Awareness of and ready access to skills and knowledge for data stewardship (4)
 - Training to support the development of key skills and knowledge for data stewardship (5)
 - Senior management see enough value in data stewardship to promote and resource it (6)
 - Requirements from publishers and funders for the availability of data outputs (7)
 - Demands from funders or commissioning organisation to deliver impact from data (8)
 - Other (please specify) (9) _____
-

Question 26

What successful methods/approaches has your service used to engage with research data producers?

Barriers to data stewardship services

Question 27

To what extent do you see each of the following as barriers to adopting good data stewardship at your organisation?

	Least significant (1)	Some significance (2)	Highly significant (3)
Duplication of effort with similar organisations or existing services (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Legal and ethical regulatory environment (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of buy-in from senior managers or researchers (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Difficulty changing stakeholders' attitudes or practices (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of incentives/ rewards for data stewardship compared with journal publication (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of clarity from funders in support for data management costs (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Question 28

What other barriers are you aware of that impact adoption of good data stewardship practices?

Page Break

Sharing your lessons and experiences

Question 29

And finally, what do you see as the main lessons about the development of your Data Stewardship services that you would pass on to similar organisations?

End of Block: Block 3
